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Handwritten Diary (Volume Two)

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The Naming of the Series of Works *Rainbow Portraits*

Wednesday, December 14, 2000

The series of works with dimensions of 45×45cm is named *Rainbow Portraits* (《彩虹寫真》). The final ten pieces have been mostly completed, though some are unsatisfactory and require revisions. These donated works are not only a summary of my *Dotted Strokes Realism* (《點化具象》) series, but also a sincere message to humanity at the turn of the century. Even though they are scattered among the public, their effectiveness relies on the accepting of my efforts by the people. The *Rainbow Portraits* is a direct expression following *Chronicles of Space and Time* (《時空書寫》), embodying the Zen of writing, presenting the true essence

of symbolic significance. It confirms what's seen, sensed, intimately felt, affixed, collided with, and touched. It's the residue of those burning with life. Its paradox lies in the genuine desire, longing, pursuit, and search of life in the hands, the deconstruction of noble passion, or one might say, self-awareness. This naturally includes self-criticism or praise, a remedy for some and a tonic for others. For those in good health, it is an offering of my communication or text. Its "Rainbow" finds solace in solidification, or the return of the soul to its home.

"Accepting Alms" and "To Bestow upon Fate"

September 2004

December 26, 1994, to December 26, 2000, marks the anniversary of my emergence from the urban setting to establish my studio. In gratitude for the various forms of assistance from friends who have selflessly supported me over the years, I dedicated a year to create, offering my work as a way to repay the debt of gratitude owed in every moment. This act can be seen as "to bestow upon fate," and in doing so, I also welcomed new "debts." Moreover, as individuals, we owe our existence to our parents, and everything acquired after that is bestowed by the society. Therefore, the care and criticism from friends are also a form of "debt." I consider friendships and the like as debts to be repaid through my lifelong work.

On December 26, 2000, at Daheishan Studio, I hosted the first "Open Studio Exhibition" since starting my work there. Using "Accepting alms" and "To bestow upon fate," I gifted over thirty pieces from the *Rainbow Portraits* series to friends who had wholeheartedly assisted me. This interactive "Open Studio Exhibition" was a form of artistic "sowing," likely the first of its kind in China. I still remember the scene vividly—it was like a festive occasion, with a huge crowd, firecrackers bursting, and friends gathering to feast and celebrate with hearty meals and drinks. Those who received the artworks were especially joyous and delighted.

Looking back, this open exhibition was indeed a

Figure 1. Yu Zhenli. *Rainbow Portrait*. Mixed media, 65×80cm, 2000.

genuine interaction. It wasn't just about the interactive format of the on-site exhibition; I delivered a speech at the opening ceremony, announced the list of recipients for the paintings, and invited the audience to enter the

studio to tour and appreciate the *Rainbow Portraits* works. Friends listed on the recipient list selected their preferred pieces in the studio, and then we all raised our glasses together, chatting freely. Behind this interactive

Figure 2. Yu Zhenli. *Rainbow Portrait No.3*. Mixed media, 45×45cm, 2000.

scene was not only the interaction of many years of life experiences but also the interaction of reason and emotion, spirit and matter, art and life. This exhibition truly achieved the integration of art and the people.

In the first three years of the 21st century, I also participated in several domestic exhibitions. Firstly, I would like to explain why I did not participate in the invitation exhibition for *20th Century Chinese Oil Painting*. It was not because I refused to or withdrew from the Chinese oil painting scene, but rather due to receiving the invitation very late. Additionally, my

elderly mother suffered a broken leg, and there were financial constraints during the construction process of the studio, as well as transportation issues. These circumstances led to missing out on an important opportunity to meet.

Therefore, to make up for it, in the first month of the new century, I participated in the *Open I: K Space Establishment Press Conference and First Exhibition* at K Space in Shenyang, curated by Ma Shang and others. Following that, I gave lectures at universities such as Nankai University in Tianjin, where I addressed

Figure 3. Yu Zhenli reading the list of friends to whom he gifted *Rainbow Portrait* artworks, December 26, 2000.

misunderstandings between myself and critics. In 2002, I was involved in the planning of the *8+1: Dalian Modern Art Exhibition* and created three large paintings titled *Water in the Sky* (《天上之水》). In April of the same year, I participated in the *First China Art Triennial Exhibition*. In 2003, I participated in the *Open Era* exhibition at the National Art Museum of China. At the end of the year, I participated in the *Metaphysical Abstract Art Exhibition* at the Shanghai Art Museum. All these exhibitions featured new works, naturally positioning me as an oil painting artist.

Turning my studio into a complete work requires continuous expansion, documentation, and a lifelong commitment to its completion. This is because constructing the studio is a process of communication with society through “Accepting Alms,” especially in terms of sourcing materials and understanding the overall

concept of artistic creation. In early 2003, the painter Yu Jin mobilized students from schools and, with the support of the principal and others, collected empty bottles from the entire school. Later, I publicly expressed my thoughts in the form of an open letter, and at that time, more than fifty people responded to my “desire.” Thousands of empty bottles were gathered in the studio and were turned into artworks. The next step is to issue a nationwide public letter of collection. Of course, ten thousand is not too many, nor is one too few. On December 26, 2003, the open letter “Collecting Empty Bottles” I sent to society was the practical realization of this idea. Eight large-scale installation sculptures have now been completed, naturally forming a unified language with the studio and the environment, representing the expansion of my abstract painting language.

To Reciprocate with Little Gestures to Bring Peace to the Heart

January 13, 2014, Lunar December 13th, Monday

When swallows fly in, they are bound to dispel the cold—both body and mind are burdened due to external obstacles, like swallows lingering under eaves. We lose some, gain some; spreading our wings and flying freely, we discard treasures like Mount Jinshan. Under the same sky, even the ugly ox finds peace in the snow. Let the heart find peace. (喚燕來必消寒——身心重負物阻攔，還體如燕恩屋簷，多少失，少多算，展翅舒飛扔金山，亦同天，醜牛雪中臥心安。還心定。)

Furthermore, reciprocating little by little is also a form of reciprocation, bringing peace to the heart. With determination, obstacles are removed, making the mirror clear and bright. The sun melts away, awaiting the arrival of the moon; the sun energy born in the twelfth lunar month melts the ice, and after spring awakening, the mirror becomes new. Observing deeply within oneself, one is free and without desire; one can go far with determination. (又。回敬點滴意得還，還心定，定力除障淨鏡圓。圓融期待月謝陽，陽生臘月寒冰開，開顏春醒新明鏡，種子五體深地觀，觀自在，無求志必遠。)

Here's an opening poem or verse to ease the flow of energy in the three meridians. The other day, I shook hands with Mr. Shang. My life's major works mostly wander afar, leaving behind a basketful of money to spark new inspiration. Why not first express gratitude to the nearby villagers who have paid attention to and appre-

ciated my work? Consider it a small red envelope for the New Year, a gesture of friendship and communication. Those notions of “never meeting again” and “building high walls” are just self-preservation talk. Nowadays, everyone cares about societal life, aren't we all united in spirit? Where can there be room for the arrogance of isolation and strength? Today, I take out ten thousand to distribute among ten households, a small gesture of thanks, where the gift is light, with no need for heavy returns.

Since the sale of the work *Sublimation* (《昇華》), the hat of poverty that the ugly person used to wear has been taken off by society. In alleviating the situation, the heart does not forget the younger brothers who have followed for many years, as well as countless relatives and friends. With over a million dispersed, it greatly alleviated one's suppression and heavy burdens, rekindling the cooled heart with warmth. It is a true choice of “oceanic consciousness” to share happiness, which will keep the eyes clear, the steps firm, the dreams sweet, the body radiant like jade, and the soul peacefully returning to the body.

Sending paintings as gifts to dear friends again, bestowing grace like the surging waves of the ocean. Amidst the crowd, the swallows soar freely as the waves crash, embodying the poetic inspiration of the celestial realm.

Still Offering Gifts for Tranquility

January 25, 2014, Lunar December 25th, Saturday

The existence of the soul is acquired through loss and injury to the body, echoing the profound pronouncement of the great philosopher Socrates, and sharing similarities with the teachings of Laozi from a century earlier, “Diminish and again diminish, until one arrives at non-action.” Half a month ago, due to my letting go of concerns, I allowed Mr. Shang to take away the artwork without stepping out of my door. Though the compensation received was far from the agreement, considering the well-being of my body and mind, seeking tranquility, I have transformed previous entanglements or feelings of pain, turning depression into cheerfulness. Excellent! Why not, on the basis of improving the lives of relatives and friends, donate the surplus to support local artistic creation, providing some funding for independent seekers of truth!

“Tranquility” cannot accommodate too many material possessions. Between excessive personal desires and those who have dedicated their lives to art without material rewards but have resonated with the spirit of time and space, I choose to sympathize with the latter. Because I have spent my whole life quietly seeking, longing for support or reward, now that Mr. Shang is gradually awakening to art, and the ugly person's finances have improved, why not provide a little more help or dedication to fellow travelers and disciples in distress? As Zhuangzi said in the chapter “Gengsang Chu,” “If one wants tranquility, then one should have a calm spirit. If one wants the spirit, then one should follow one's heart. If one wants to act, then one should do so appropriately. Such is the way of the sage.” Although I cannot perform the acts of a sage, I

Figure 4. Dabei Mountain Video Art Space (大黑山影像藝術空間) inscribed by Yu Zhenli.

can make small contributions.

During lunchtime, Mr. Shang came to pay for the artworks and casually asked for my figure sketches from the 1980s. I readily handed them over (about a hundred pieces), in the pursuit of tranquility and harmony of the heart. Subsequently, I invited Wang Lianyi to accompany

me to the bank and deposited a million for the “8+1” exhibition, to be used for exhibition organization, lectures, awards, and other funds. The details will be announced on an appropriate day, bringing clarity to my vision and peace to my heart upon returning to the mountains.

The Emergence of the 8+1 Visual Art Exhibition

May 26, 2014, Lunar April 28th, Monday

Ma Shang called to inform me that he has already arranged for more than ten participants to join the *8+1 Visual Art Exhibition*, inviting almost all those involved in visual arts from Liaoning. What's more, he introduced two participants from Beijing and one from Shandong, indicating that this exhibition greatly extends the range of participation across regions, especially stepping out from the craftsmanship of painting and towards closer proximity to visual art with more imagery, touch, and

originality. Of course, this also presents a new intellectual field for the contemporary art scene in our city and marks an important step towards transforming my studio into a true playground for artistic experimentation. Thus, I thank Ma Shang for his organization and efforts.

At my solo exhibition in Beijing last October, Ma Shang discussed with me the next steps I could take. After returning to Shenyang, he didn't waste any time. Within a few days, he brought his equipment and

Figure 6. *The Model Effect—The Seventh 8+1 Art Exhibition* was displayed outdoors at Xinghai Square in Dalian, January 2015.

the “8+1” Art Salon activities. The funds intended for the “8+1” art activities are about to be handed over. With figures like Qu Zhenwei, Ma Shang, Zhu Xikun and others serving as the academic-oriented pillars, the symbol of the emerging avant-garde in contemporary art salons in Dalian, “Salon” has been established. In its future development, the ugly person is no longer the “only one” but rather “one of many.”

Perhaps due to the identity of a mentor and the habit of “doing mass art” in the 1970s and 1980s, although my concerns have shifted from “popularization” to “improvement” consciousness, guiding contemporary newcomers seems incongruous given my self-perceived “marginalized” identity and art. Therefore, from the first *8+1: Dalian Modern Art Exhibition* in 2002, after ten years of self-doubt or depression, the studio and environmental art created with urban garbage have come to a close, and the “8+1” Dalian Contemporary Art has

hosted six sessions. Although effective, it is not sufficiently enlarged, especially in terms of ideas, posing questions, critical references, and the responsibility of intellectuals. It awaits new people with new thinking. Otherwise, it will be a mediocre and dull “stew.” Therefore, for the ugly person who is always on the verge of death, letting go and allowing young newcomers to freely associate is not a joyful thing?

Writing this *Handwritten Diary* has been like having one foot off the ground for many years without finding solid ground. Finally, I see the other foot touching down. Letting go is like releasing the soul and relaxing—I firmly believe that just as the new moon symbolizes the first day, there will be a full moon on the fifteenth day. I can now peacefully create my works, even if they only contribute modestly to the local scenery. Letting go also allows oneself to rest with peace of mind.

The Planning Proposal for the “Models” Exhibition and Wine Reception

November 24, 2014, Lunar October 3rd, Monday

In the evening, Zhu Xikun arrived and handed over the

planning proposal for the seventh “8+1” exhibition. I brie-

Figure 7. Artist Yu Zhenli walking in Dahei Mountain.

fly skimmed through it and found it to be more meticulous, organized, and concise compared to previous “8+1” exhibition plans. It is the most well-planned one I have encountered so far.

With the theme of “Models, Image Generation, Public Context,” the exhibition aims to “explore the practice and methodology of experimental art, which has become a significant contemporary art subject worthy of attention. Due to the pioneering, public, and everyday nature of experimental art, it forms a powerful gravitational field. Experimental art is full of various possibilities. This exhibition seeks to introduce and reflect the achievements of artists in the field of experimental art to the audience.”

Concept Definition: “... This model effect has become a cultural public context, where everyone appreciates each other, imitates each other, learns from each other, and subverts each other!”

Summarized very clearly—my “ideas” were swiftly planned into a scheme by him, which surpasses my capability.

Wine Reception—Lao Zhu arrived with his wife, evidently prepared for the wine reception. I quickly found snacks from the refrigerator and plated a few ready-made dishes on small plates. He dominated the conversation, and I responded to each point. Our exchange flowed smoothly without any barriers, perhaps because we shared mutual respect. Last night, he was still at Gao Minglu’s place, and today he came up to the mountain to discuss the “Models” of the “8+1” exhibition on December 26th. His sense of responsibility and vitality are undiminished from previous years. After reviewing his proposal, I truly admire it. He is indeed a genuine curator of contemporary art, no doubt about it.

The Transfer of Ownership of the “8+1” Fund

December 1, 2014, Lunar October 10th, Monday

Contributing one million RMB, originally allocated for the activities of the 8+1: Dalian Modern Art Exhibition and other events, the remaining funds from this year's solo exhibition for Jiang Jimin and the inaugural *Image Art Exhibition* have now been transferred under the participation of Wang Lianyi, with Qu Zhenwei taking over as the new custodian. With him appointed as the director of “8+1,” the weighty burden that had long pressed on my heart has finally been lifted.

The “8+1” art activities were initiated in 2002, spurred by the anticipation of numerous avant-garde artists in Dalian. It all began with the sale of the artwork *Silk Road in A Major* (《絲綢之路 A 大調》) and was swiftly organized by key figures such as Xu Changjian, Qu Zhenwei, Yang Hong, and Li You. As I recognized them, they were undoubtedly the most outstanding avant-garde artists in contemporary Dalian. Figures like Yang Maoyuan and Mou Daqi, strictly speaking, were encouraged by me to participate in the exhibition as part

of my advocacy for contemporary consciousness. With the studio's construction having taken shape over the years, the exhibition was continued in 2010 and has since been held six times. The funds obtained from selling artworks, earmarked for the development of Dalian's art scene, have garnered media attention. However, feeling uneasy about personally controlling the funds, I entrusted Qu Zhenwei with the role of director to manage the fund. This move not only signifies trust but also indicates that the fund is not for my manipulation. Since it is intended for public welfare, it should not be under my control.

The handover was completed at the Industrial and Commercial Bank of China. For the first time, he withdrew thirty thousand yuan to support Xu Changjian's solo exhibition in Beijing. This also brought solace to me and eased my mind.

[Yu Zhenli Art Museum provides the article]

Translator and editor: Li Yang

Editor's Notes:

After exploring Yu Zhenli's early works, his construction of a studio in the mountains, and his Chinese abstract morphological expressionism paintings, this issue will review Yu Zhenli and the contemporary art scene in Dalian. The first article will analyze some often overlooked details in his life and work, as well as summarize the events surrounding his establishment of the 8+1 Art Fund. The second article will compile excerpts from his *Handwritten Diary*, focusing on his connections with the Dalian art community, providing us with a closer perspective on the life of an artist.

編者按：

在探討于振立的早期創作、上山建造工作室以及他的抽象寫意主義繪畫之後，這期將回顧于振立與大連的當代藝術生態。以一篇評論文章分析他生活與創作中一些不常被關注的細節，和他創辦 8+1 藝術基金的事件匯總。第二篇是將其《手記》中一些涉及他與大連藝術界相關的文字進行摘寫匯總，讓我們以更近的視角理解一個藝術家的生存狀態。